

Respect for Seleukid Suzerainty: The Imitative Victory Coinage of the Sistan Ariaspi

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The victory coinage bearing the name Antiochos (SC 226-228), currently attributed to the province of Drangiana during the co-regency of Seleukos and Antiochos, exhibits a progressive deterioration of iconography and epigraphy over the duration of its emission. It has the characteristics of an imitative coinage, struck over a prolonged period, rather than the 14 years of the co-regency. Die study reveals stages of iconographic deterioration, enabling the coinage to be categorized into three groups, each with its own progressively degraded iconography and epigraphy. During its emission a local artistic tradition, possibly reflecting a longstanding Indian influence appears in the iconography of the obverse, and what appears to be an early Brahmi script eventually displaces Greek on the reverse. This is interpreted to reflect contemporary Mauryan cultural and linguistic influences, the result of interaction with adjacent Arachosia. Plausibly, the coinage was struck intermittently in the period c. 281-175 BC by the Ariaspi, the semi-autonomous people of the Sistan depression in Drangiana, who acknowledged Seleukid suzerainty in the choice of coin type and legend.

BACKGROUND

Early last century Edward Rapson described some coins from what he believed to be a hoard originating “from the neighbourhood of Kuh-i-Taftan (S.E.Persia)” in Baluchistan (*IGCH* 1803) that was buried around 140 BC.¹ The largest component of the coins he described consisted of drachms and fractions bearing a strikingly crude iconography based on what we now recognise as the victory, or trophy coinage of Susa,² but bearing the name of Antiochos, rather than Seleukos. Rapson attributed these coins to “the barbarous tribes inhabiting this desolate region” of Baluchistan.³ He suggested, that when more examples became available that “it is likely that the general laws which govern the changes which types undergo when they pass through a number of successive stages of unintelligent copying” will yield insight into the origin of the coinage.⁴ Three decades later, Newell recorded three more examples of the coinage.⁵ He observed that the coins “seem only to come from Baluchistan - a sure indication of the eastern origin of their prototypes.” The

¹ Rapson (1904); Kuh-i-Taftan 1902 Hoard (*IGCH* 1803).

² Called ‘trophy coinage’ by Houghton and Lorber 2002, it is more correctly labelled ‘victory coinage’ for the reverse depicts Nike crowning a trophy with a laurel wreath in a clear celebration of victory, one that is best associated with Seleukos’s victory over Antigonos at Ipsos in 301 BC. Iossif (2004): 249–271; Marest-Caffey (2016) 1-63, for a comprehensive analysis of the iconography and chronology of the Susa victory coinage.

³ As referred to by Rapson, Baluchistan included part of southern and southwestern Afghanistan extending into south-eastern Iran and western Pakistan. The territory of the Baloch people, it was more extensive than the present-day province of Baluchistan in Pakistan.

⁴ Rapson (1904): 321.

⁵ Newell (1938): pl. LVI, 7-9.

latter he attributed to a mint at Persepolis.⁶ Over the following four decades less than two dozen additional specimens came to light. These were detailed in a corpus by Houghton,⁷ an adjunct to his reattribution of the victory coinage from Persepolis to Susa. He considered that the imitative coins constituted a “coherent single series,” the result of “the work of a single school of die cutters” that originated “on the western edge of the Baluchistan desert,”⁸ an attribution he later detailed more specifically “to the Helmand Valley (Seistan).”⁹ Dating the coinage to the period following the accession of Antiochos I, he stated that “a terminal date for the series cannot be established with accuracy.”¹⁰ Later he wrote that the coinage “was evidently the product of a local mint operating during the reign of Antiochos I.”¹¹ A decade later, Houghton and Lorber attributed the coinage (SC 226-228) to the province of Drangiana, struck in the period “294-281 BC, or later.”¹² They suggested that “the controls of this trophy coinage cannot be accounted for as mere imitations, but seem to attest to the operation of an official mint.” In considering the chronology, they reasoned that “the coregency seems a more plausible context for the opening of this mint than the years after the death of Seleucus, when Antiochos was occupied in the west.” Many new examples of the coinage have come to light recently, probably the result of an undocumented hoard that came to market in the period 2018-2020.¹³ Presented in the catalogue (detailed at the end of this paper) these newly identified coins have more than doubled the corpus of known examples, bringing a diversity of styles that challenges the interpretation that this was an official Seleukid coinage.

DISCUSSION

The coinage is classified into three distinct groups of progressively degraded iconography and epigraphy (Figure 1). The defining characteristics of each group are summarized in Table 1. Two successive series of issues are recognised within each of the first two groups (denoted by the second digit in the type classification of the catalogue). Degradational changes in iconography from one group to the next are permanent and flow across all the denominations in each group. Fractional denominations, primarily hemidrachm and obol, are identified in all groups (Table 2).

Even at its best in Group 1 (Plate 1, 1-12), the iconography is a crude copy of that of the Susa prototype (Figure 1a).¹⁴ The bull’s horn projecting in front of the helmet from the far side, a distinctive composite perspective feature of the Susa prototype,¹⁵ is absent from all but the first two obverse dies of the coinage. On the reverse, much of the detail of the trophy is either

⁶ *Ibid.*: 159.

⁷ Houghton (1980): 11-13.

⁸ *Ibid.*: 12.

⁹ Houghton and Lorber (2002): 88. Seistan is an alternative spelling of Sistan. The Sistan depression, also termed the Sistan Basin, is a geomorphic entity, an endorheic basin located on the border of present-day Iran (Sistan and Baluchistan Province) and southern Afghanistan (Nimruz, Helmand and Farah Provinces). It encompasses the lower reaches of the Helmand River, which empties into Lake Hamoun on the western side of the Sistan depression; refer to Figure 6.

¹⁰ Houghton (1980): 13.

¹¹ Houghton (1983): 108; CSE 1103-1119 subsequently donated to the collection of the American Numismatic Society in 1984.

¹² Houghton and Lorber (2002): 88-89. The Sistan depression was part of the Achaemenid satrapy of Drangiana.

¹³ No details of the find location, or a comprehensive outline of the hoard content are known to the author.

¹⁴ Illustrated coin from the author’s collection; Marest-Caffety AJN 28, Victory Coinage 2.5, 209, dies A10/P11, Pl. 15, 209 (this coin) from Triton XVIII (2015), 713; Cederlind 106 (1996), 814; Peus 340 (1994), 476.

¹⁵ Marest-Caffety (2016): 18.

Susa Prototype

Group 1
Series 1

Group 1
Series 2

Group 2
Series 1

Group 2
Series 2

Group 3

Figure 1. Iconographic Progression
(images enlarged x 1.5).

missing or poorly depicted. For example, the Star of Vergina that emblazons the shield on the prototype is missing. Other than on the first coin in the sequence, Nike appears to be missing her left arm, raising the wreath with her extended right hand only. Her left wing progressively shrinks, then disappears completely. The crowning laurel wreath held in her two outstretched hands on the prototype disappears. Hemispherical globules become defining elements of the reverse iconography from Group 2 onwards. They replace the detail of the upper body armour and helmet on the trophy. Continued deterioration in the detail of the iconography of both obverse and reverse leads eventually to abstraction of components of the iconography on Group 3, the details of which can only be appreciated with knowledge of the Susa prototype.

Table 1. Sequence summary.

Mint Controls	Iconographic and Epigraphic Characteristics
Group 1 (c. 281-261 BC)	
<i>Series 1</i>	<i>Obverse:</i> after the first two dies the forward direct bull's horn in front of the helmet is absent.
IA	
I	<i>Reverse:</i> Nike crowns trophy with poorly defined laurel wreath. Both of Nike's wings are fully outlined.
AA	
A	<i>Border:</i> crudely dotted border both sides.
AI	<i>Legend:</i> BACIAEΩC or BACIAEOC, ANTIOXOY or ANTIOX.
CA	Royal title omitted from all but one obol.
<i>Series 2</i>	<i>Obverse:</i> Initially in the style of Series 1, then becoming more varied. The feline skin tied around the neck is either absent, or reduced to the depiction of the knotted paws.
CI	
ΛI	<i>Reverse:</i> Nike's l. wing is reduced to vestigial form defined by a single line. The crowning wreath held by Nike is poorly defined or absent.
Λ	
CD	<i>Border:</i> initially a crudely dotted border both sides, after which the rev. border is discarded on the later examples.
CO	
None	<i>Legend:</i> IACIAIOC, IACIAE•C or IACIA on l.; ANTIOXOY or ANTIOX• on r. sometimes placement reversed, with some drachms lacking a legend. After the first specimen, there is no legend on the obols of Series 2.

Group 2

(c. 250-200 BC)

<p><i>Series 1</i></p> <p>PI</p> <p>Λ</p> <p>ΛI</p> <p>A</p> <p>AD</p> <p>E</p>	<p><i>Obverse:</i> the feline skin tied around the neck of the male head is reduced to a few lines in an inverted V beneath the neck. The neck guard of the helmet is depicted without leopard skin spots and develops a rippled structure as if its confused with falling locks of long hair from the back of the head.</p> <p><i>Reverse:</i> Nike's l. wing is no longer depicted after the first issue in this group. The helmet, upper torso armour of the trophy are defined by three or five hemispherical globules (three globules on the smaller fractions) coalesced into a human form; a defining characteristic that distinguishes Group 2 from the preceding emission.</p> <p><i>Border:</i> initially a coarsely dotted obv. border that is discarded completely after the first few dies.</p> <p><i>Legend:</i> Varied forms downward on l. including DACIAE, IACIAE, ACIAEΩ; on l., ANTIOXOY or ANTIOX on r. Legend absent on some examples. Fractions anepigraphic. Notable is either a retrograde Aramaic (<i>resh, zain</i>) or Brahmi (<i>jha, ra</i>) mint control PI on the first drachm. The latter would support the interpretation of the letter form D in the royal title and the mint control AD as being Brahmi letter <i>dha</i>.</p>
<p><i>Series 2</i></p> <p>None</p>	<p><i>Obverse:</i> the substantial nose on the male head is enhanced further, into a sharp beak-like form, given even greater prominence on the last of the series by the use of a strongly engraved outline to delineate this facial feature.</p> <p><i>Reverse:</i> initially a continuation of Series 1 but becoming less detailed on the later dies.</p> <p><i>Legend:</i> Varied forms downward on l. including IDCIA, DACIAE, ACIAE, DACIAEΩ, DAIA, DACIAC, IACIAE, DAEIAC, DACIAEΩC (engraved in retrograde) on l., ANTIOXOY, ANTIOX, or ANTIOY on r. The fractions are anepigraphic.</p>

Group 3

(c. 200-175 BC)

<p>ΛIPI</p> <p>None</p>	<p><i>Obverse:</i> elements of helmet ornamentation are barely recognizable. On one drachm the bull's ear and the volute termination of the helmet visor are absent. The panther skin tied around the neck is absent. On the fractions the helmet and visage are reduced to a barely recognizable abstraction.</p> <p><i>Reverse:</i> in its final form the trophy is reduced to a barely recognisable form, while Nike is depicted in a rudimentary form, with legs barely discernible. On one drachm two dotted vertical elements are introduced between Nike and the trophy.</p> <p><i>Border:</i> Coarsely dotted obverse border on drachms.</p> <p><i>Legend:</i> Either very blundered Greek or Brahmi (?) script Λ I Π E on one drachm, another with a Brahmi mint mark ΛIPI. The fractions are anepigraphic.</p>
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Table 2. Observed number of obverse dies.

Group	Drachm	Hemidrachm	Trihemiobol	Obol	Hemiobol
1.1	4	2	-	6	-
1.2	6	1	-	7	-
2.1	5.5*	3	-	2	-
2.2	14.5	1	-	1	1
3	2	1	1	1	-
	32	8	1	17	1

* Fractional die count indicates a die shared by two series.

In the course of the coinage mint controls disappear, legends become increasingly blundered, and Brahmi characters appear interspersed with Greek letters in Group 2. These fully displace Greek script on Group 3. Finely dotted borders become coarser, only to disappear, initially from the reverse on Group 1.1, followed shortly thereafter by that of the obverse on Group 2.1. These increasing departures from the Susa prototype are the basis on which the coinage is sequenced. They suggest that the coinage was struck over an extended period of time, the result of repeated copying, by which the detail and significance of the iconography was progressively lost. This is the hallmark of an immobilised imitative coinage, rather than an official Seleukid emission.

PROGRESSION

Degenerative iconographic changes are apparent on almost every successive die in Group 1. After the first two obverse dies, the bull's horn that projects in front of the helmet is dropped from the iconography. The anticlockwise legend convention of prototype is neglected, after which there is a reversal of the right and left placement convention of the royal title and king's name respectively. Nike's outstretched arms are reduced to one, while the crowning laurel wreath she holds above the trophy disappears by the last of Group 1.1. Notable is Cat. No. 4 on which a second arm, attached to Nike's torso below her right arm extends toward the top of the body armour of the trophy (Figure 1, 4). This illustrates the die engraver's poor understanding of the prototype and the symbolism of the image.

Based on close similarity of obverse style, the first coins of Group 1.2 are a direct extension of Group 1.1 from which they are differentiated by key elements of epigraphy and iconography. On the earliest examples the feline skin tied around the neck of the male head is missing from dies A5 and A6. It reappears on later dies, albeit in a barely recognizable form delineated by a few simple lines. With one exception the royal title is placed on the left of the reverse. At times the genitive of the name of the king is abbreviated to ANTIOX, while the legend is absent on two drachms and most of the obols. The latter bear no mint control but are sequenced in Group 1.2, rather than Group 2, due to the more detailed depiction of the trophy. On most of the coins of Group 1.2 Nike's left wing, that appearing between her body and the trophy, is reduced to a vestigial depiction, often consisting of a single line, or absent. The dotted reverse border disappears in the course of Group 1.2, while the dotted obverse border is coarsely defined.

Group 2 is distinguished from Group 1 by a further deterioration in the detail of the reverse iconography. Hemispherical globules of various sizes, are a major component of the engravers' repertoire. The helmet of the trophy is reduced to a large globule that sits atop the body armour, as if a head. The upper torso body armour is depicted initially by a pair of large globules, then four globules stacked in two pairs of different diameters, the latter reduced to a single pair on the small diameter obols. After an initial depiction of the wreath in Nike's extended right hand, this component of the iconography disappears. On the obverse, the feline skin tied around the neck of the male head is reduced to a few scribbled lines, an abstraction of the knot in the feline skin before the neck on the Susa prototype. Frequently this element of the iconography appears as a Λ shape, its limbs spread wide beneath the neck truncation of the helmeted head. It bears no resemblance to the feline skin on the Susa prototype, or the depiction on Group 1. Such is the degree of abstraction of this element of the iconography, that without knowledge of the prototype, the intended depiction of these lines would be unknown. Further deterioration in the iconography occurs with the neck guard of the helmet, which is depicted frequently as a rippled structure, lacking the curvature of the original neck guard, and the spots of the leopard skin are absent.

A coarsely dotted obverse border appears on the first of the drachms and obols of Group 2, before being disappearing from the balance of the group. All the denominations of Group 2 exhibit a more strongly concave reverse fabric than Group 1, suggesting a change in the construction of the reverse dies. This is co-incident with the appearance of the effects of die rust on both sides of drachms struck from a number of well-worn dies. From the latter it is inferred that Group 2 was struck from ferrous dies, a departure from the bronze dies of Group 1. The difficulty of engraving hard ferrous dies may have contributed to the iconographic degeneration of Group 2 with easily cut hemispherical globules substituted for the finer detail of the trophy armour and helmet. The drachms of Group 2.1 continue the use of control marks as occurred in Group 1. This ceases with Group 2.2. It is the presence or absence of control marks that is the primary differentiating characteristic that distinguishes the two series of Group 2. However, the two series are obverse die linked by A16, which first saw use in Group 2.2 indicating that there was a chronological overlap between the end of Group 2.1 and the start of 2.2. For the most part the coins of Group 2.2 are of a uniform style, until the last few examples (Cat. Nos. 47-49), which are so different, that it is possible that two phases of striking are represented in Group 2.2. Based on the obverse die count (Table 2), Group 2.2 represents the largest component of the coinage in which 45 percent of the total drachm dies are represented.

Consisting of four coins, Group 3 is poorly represented in the sample. On the drachms of this group, details of the helmeted head are confused, or missing, although the overall design is still recognizable against its prototype. Equally so the reverse, where aberrant elements are present, including two dotted vertical lines between Nike and the trophy on one example (Figure 1, 50). Further degraded imagery is found on the Group 3 trihemiobol, where the obverse is reduced to a barely recognizable abstraction of a helmeted head; completely missing are the facial features, but for a ridge extending from the front of the helmet representing the line of the nose (Figure 1, 62). Despite this, the detail of the reverse clearly places this coin as a component of the Group 3 emission. Rapson documented a Group 3 hemidrachm (Rapson, Class B2) found with seven coins

of Group 2 (Rapson, Class B1) in the Kuh-i-Taftan Hoard (IGCH 1803),¹⁶ strengthening the inferred geographic association of this abstracted type with the preceding group. However, the magnitude of the iconographic deterioration suggests that there was a significant time break between the striking of Groups 2 and 3.

A Curious Eye and a Significant Nose

Two unusual facial features appear at various times in the coinage. These are suggestive of an eastern, or Indian cultural influence on the coinage. Firstly, the depiction of a frontal eye, rather than an eye in profile appears on the male head on two coins, one in Group 1 (Cat. No. 4; Figure 1, 4) and the other on the last of Group 2 (Cat. No. 49, Figure 1, 49). Although reminiscent of the archaized eye found on 5th century BC Athenian coinage it is more subtly defined. An identical depiction is found on many of the contemporary imitative Alexandrine issues of Arachosia.¹⁷ The latter was situated immediately to the east of the province of Drangiana, and the Sistan depression. The shared depiction of this eye on the imitative coinages of both provinces may reflect a shared heritage arising from historic trade and other interactions between the two provinces, plus an Indian (Mauryan) influence among the engravers of the dies from which these coins were struck. In the 3rd century BC Arachosia was under the governance of a succession of Mauryan kings following the agreement struck between Seleukos I and Chandragupta in c. 305/4 BC.¹⁸ Additional iconographic support for this inferred Indian influence is found in the reverse of Cat. No. 4, on which Nike is depicted with two right arms, reminiscent of the depiction of some multi-armed Hindu deities (Figure 1, 4).

Another feature of the iconography is the increasingly accentuated nose of the male head compared to that of the Susa prototype (Figure 1). This progresses in its development from a large nose to become a prominent almost beak-like depiction on the last of Group 2.2. On the iconography of the Group 3 trihemiobol there is a linear protrusion descending from the front of the helmet, at first glance resembling a nose guard, but clearly an abstraction of the nose (Figure 1, 62). This is the only facial feature retained in the abstraction, and it emphasises the significance of the nose in the local artistic tradition. It may reflect a pre-existing artistic tradition. The prominence of the nose has echoes of the artistic tradition of an ancient culture in the region, that of the Mehrgarh VII culture dating to the 3rd millennium BC, archaeological remains of which have been the subject of excavation in eastern Baluchistan (Arachosia) in the vicinity of Quetta.¹⁹ This influenced the artistic tradition of the succeeding Indus Valley Harappan civilization, which gave prominent expression to the sharp elongated nose described on earthenware statues from the earliest archaeological excavations in Baluchistan.²⁰ This artistic device appears to have survived in the region long after the demise of these civilizations, assisted perhaps by religious association with early depictions of fertility gods such as the *Zhob* mother-goddess in the Mehrgarh VII culture²¹ that were carried

¹⁶ Rapson (1904): 317-318.

¹⁷ Miller (2010): East Arachosia (Quetta) Hoard, 2002 (CH 10.275) nos. 122, 140, 141, 143, 145, 164, 168, 174 and 179.

¹⁸ Houghton and Lorber (2002): 1; Wheatley (2014): 503-508; Holt (1993).

¹⁹ Shaffer and Thapar (1992) 242, and 245-246, fig. 4.

²⁰ Dani and Thapar (1992): 285, figs. 4-5.

²¹ Shaffer and Thapar (1992): 245-246, fig. 4.

through time to succeeding cultures in the region. Figurines of the *Zhob* type were found in the excavations at Shahr-i-Sokhta the largest Bronze age site in the Sistan depression and are thought to be the result of trade with the Indus Valley Harappan culture 800 km to the east.²² A similarly exaggerated nose is also found on some of the late 3rd century BC imitative Alexanders from the East Arachosia (Quetta) Hoard (CH 10.275).²³

The significance of the development of an accentuated nose on the coinage is twofold. It is a pointer to the origin of the coinage in the easternmost part of the Seleukid empire, on the frontier of Indian cultural influence.²⁴ The latter was recognized with the ceding of administrative control of eastern Arachosia to the Mauryan king Chandragupta by Seleukos in c. 305/4 BC, a pact reconfirmed a century later between Antiochos III and Sophagesenus.²⁵ Secondly, a waning Greek artistic influence, displaced by a pre-existing local artistic tradition, must have been an extended process; far longer than the 14 years implied by an attribution of the coinage to the coregency of Seleukos and Antiochos (294-281 BC).

Epigraphy

Nominally, the legend on the coinage is intended to read ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΑΝΤΙΟΧΟΥ, but this rendering of the legend is completely absent (Table 1; Figure 2).

Figure 2. Epigraphy of the royal title.

²² Jarrige et al (2011): 19.

²³ Miller (2010): East Arachosia (Quetta) Hoard, 2002 (CH 10.275) nos. 116, 117, 118, 127 and 155.

²⁴ Houghton and Lorber (2002): 1.

²⁵ *Ibid*: 352.

Even on the earliest examples of Group 1.1 the legend is blundered, the royal title rendered ΒΑCΙΑΕΩC then ΒΑCΙΑΕOC rather than ΒΑΣΙΑΕΩΣ. The Greek letters Α, Σ and Ω in the royal title are replaced by Λ, C and O or a large dot, respectively. In handwritten Greek during the early Hellenistic period the letter Σ was simplified to a lunate form (C).²⁶ In numismatics the first identified occurrence of lunate *sigma* is on two rare issues of the co-regency elephant chariot type coinage of Baktria, struck in the joint names of Seleukos and Antiochos, exclusively on a much-reduced weight local weight standard (SC 279.3 and 280.3).²⁷ These epigraphic departures in the letter forms establish that from the outset the royal title in the legend was the product of less than faithful copying of the word ΒΑΣΙΑΕΩΣ.

In Group 1.2, the letter Β is rendered as Ι. In turn, this is replaced by the letter form Δ in Group 2. The latter has no precedent in Greek, or Aramaic, but notably it does exist in Brahmi script (Brahmi *dha*). Coincident with this curious introduction of the letter form Δ, the letter form C is replaced by a square form \square while the letter O in the royal title (*omicron* rather than *omega*), is replaced by a flattened form of the Greek letter Ω. On the sole example of Group 3 with a component of the legend visible to the left of Nike, the royal title is rendered as $\Psi \text{ I } \text{ I } \text{ E}$, either an extremely blundered Greek, or a crudely engraved script of Brahmi characters (Brahmi *la, ra, ga, ja*). If the former, it can only be from the hand of a die engraver completely illiterate in Greek. If crudely engraved Brahmi script, it may reflect influence and exchange with adjacent Mauryan administered Arachosia where Brahmi written Prakrit was used for the official records of the Mauryan court and administration. This curious assemblage and progression of Greek and non-Greek letter forms in the legend is without precedent in the Seleukid series struck at official mints. It is unlikely on an official coinage dating to the co-regency of Seleukos and Antiochos.

Mint controls are found on all denominations of Group 1, and Group 2.1 after which they disappear from the coinage with the exception of a single Group 3 drachm (Table 3). It is uncertain whether these constitute genuine mint marks, used in the mint's process control, or were an imitative epigraphy (pseudo-controls) that was lost in successive copying. In many cases the letters of these control marks are poorly engraved and subject to ambiguity in reading. It appears that components of Brahmi script are introduced into some of the control marks of Group 2.1, suggesting an Indian linguistic influence among the die cutters.

Table 3. Distribution of mint marks.

Group	Drachm	Hemidrachm	Obol
1.1	IA, I, AA	I, CA	A, AI, CA
1.2	CI, CD, Λ, AI	CO	Λ, none
2.1	$\Psi \text{ I}$, Λ, A, AD, E	Λ, AI	A
2.2	none	none	none
3	$\Lambda \text{ I } \square$, none	none	none

²⁶ Thompson (1912): 107-109 and 144 (Table No. 1).

²⁷ Struck from little more than a handful of dies in four denominations (tetradrachm, drachm, hemidrachm and obol) this coinage appears to have been a very short-lived, low volume, epichoric coinage, possibly a trial of a reduced weight coinage system, that was abandoned almost immediately in favour of the reduced Attic standard prevailing throughout the Seleukid realm. The coregency legend distinguished it from the far more substantial mintage of Attic weight standard counterparts which were struck exclusively in the name of Seleukos.

Notable among the mint controls is what at first glance appears to be the Brahmi control **PI** on the first of type 2.1 (Figure 3a), its position in the sequence established by the closer relationship of the obverse style to that of Group 1.2 compared to that of succeeding Group 2.1 coins. The reverse bears a vestigial depiction of Nike's right wing, similar to that found on Group 1.2, while the trophy with its three-globule head and torso depiction is a precursor to the five-globule depiction of the balance of Group 2.1 drachms. On this coin, the only completely visible letter (Y) in the right-hand component of the legend (ANTIOXOY) that was largely struck off-flan indicates that this component of the legend was rendered in Greek, albeit oriented outward so that the king's name was rendered in retrograde on the strike. This raises the possibility that the mint control was similarly engraved in retrograde, in which case its intended form on the strike would have been **IQ**, the Aramaic letters *resh, zain* (read r. to l.). A similar, though non-retrograde, Aramaic mint control has been noted on some imitative victory coinage of uncertain attribution in the name of Seleukos.²⁸ By virtue of their good style, legend, and other accompanying mint controls, the latter cannot be associated with the imitative victory coinage in the name of Antiochos. However, one of these coins may have provided a prototype for the latter. In the absence of more examples, we cannot determine with confidence whether we are dealing with a retrograde Aramaic mint control, or the introduction of a Brahmi script mint control on the first of Group 2.1, although the presence of other Brahmi letter forms in the legend and some other mint controls lends some support for the latter. For example, the letter D (Brahmi *dha*) appears as a component of one of the other mint controls, preceded by the Greek letter A (Table 3; Figure 3b). The introduction of what appear to be components of Brahmi text into the epigraphy of Group 2 suggests an Indian influence among the die engravers. This parallels the emergence of Indian artistic traditions in the iconography of Group 2. It is consistent with the inferred origin of the coinage on the eastern limit of the Seleukid empire, bordering Arachosia which was ceded to Chandragupta by Seleukos I at the conclusion of the latter's eastern anabasis.

Figure 3. Mint controls.

On the last of the Group 2.1 drachms, the letter E mint mark, like most other controls marks is poorly engraved, so as to resemble the letter F. The reverse die bearing this mark is obverse die linked to Group 2.2, which lacks mint marks. However, the progression of wear on the linking obverse die (A16) indicates that this coin was struck after the first of the Group 2.2 drachms. This suggests

²⁸ Marest-Caffey (2016); Group 5, I1 and J1 (tetradrachms), Group 6, A1 (drachm) and Group 8, A1 (obol).

that the transition between the two series of Group 2 was gradual; one in which mint marks were gradually lost, or discarded, in the copying process.

What appears to be a three-letter mint mark in Brahmi script $\Lambda I \text{𑀓}$ (Brahmi *ga, ra, da*) appears on one of the two drachms of Group 3 (Figure 3c; Cat. No. 50). The accompanying legend is struck completely off-flan. However, as noted above, on the other Group 3 drachm (Cat. No. 51; Figure 2, Group 3), what appears to be a crudely engraved Brahmi script completely displaces Greek in the legend. Apparently, by the time of Group 3, Greek script had disappeared from the epigraphy.

These epigraphic developments are further evidence for the imitative nature of the coinage, for it is improbable that the combination of two different scripts (Greek and Brahmi) observed in the royal title would result in a legible word bearing the intended meaning. In contrast to the royal title, far greater attention was paid to copying the genitive form of the king's name, ANTIOXOY in Groups 1 and 2. Despite occasional omission of the last three letters, no aberrant letter forms appear in this component of the legend, suggesting that it was more assiduously copied out of respect for the suzerain. This is an important point that has bearing on both the origins and chronology of the coinage as discussed below.

The mixing of two scripts in the epigraphy provides both chronological and geographical pointers. The earliest surviving Brahmi inscriptions date to early in the reign of the Mauryan king, Ashoka (c. 272-232 BC).²⁹ The adjacent territory of Arachosia was under Mauryan governance, so that the presence of a component of Brahmi script on the imitative victory coinage probably reflects a Mauryan cultural and linguistic influence on the eastern fringe of the Seleukid empire. Its occurrence marks the western-most extent of this influence, while the presence of Brahmi letter forms suggests that the coins bearing this script were struck no earlier than the reign of the Mauryan king Ashoka, i.e. post 272 BC. Significantly, this would mark the earliest known examples of Brahmi script on coinage, preceding by a significant margin that found on the bilingual coinage of Agathokles and Pantaleon of Bactria, struck south of the Hindu Kush in the period c.185-170 BC.³⁰

DIE AXES

Figure 4 displays the alignment of die axes on the coinage, referenced to the hands on a clock face. Apparent is the tendency towards parallel, or 12 o'clock die adjustment in the drachms. 84 percent of the drachms exhibit die axes aligned between 10 and 12 o'clock, with 37 percent adjusted precisely to 12 o'clock. An asymmetry in the distribution of alignment of the drachm die axes is evident. Few drachms exhibit axes disposed between 1-2 o'clock in contrast to the frequent occurrence between 10-11 o'clock. Possibly, this reflects a preferred working orientation of the strikers around the anvil. A similar, pattern is apparent in the hemidrachms. With the smaller fractions there is a greater dispersion of orientations, suggesting less rigorous attention to die adjustment during their striking.

²⁹ Salomon (2003): 87.

³⁰ Hoover (2013): 25-34, catalogue nos. 93, 98 and 105.

Figure 4. Alignment of die axes.

METROLOGY

The weight distribution of each denomination is summarized in Table 4 and graphically illustrated for the drachm denomination in Figure 5. The weight distribution of the drachms exhibits a strongly developed modal peak centred on 4.2 grams. Including some well-worn coins, the distribution has a mean weight of 4.06 grams with a standard deviation of 0.34 grams. It conforms closely to that expected of an Attic weight standard emission. The weight distribution of each of the fractional denominations conforms closely, within a few percent, of that which would be directly scaled from a weight standard drachm of 4.2 grams. Despite the imitative style of the coinage, precise weight adjustment of all denominations to a tightly defined standard was maintained with precision. The existence of the trihemiobol and hemiobol denominations is demonstrated in the statistical analysis summarized in Table 4. The weight of the trihemiobol is seven standard deviations less than the mean weight of the hemidrachms and almost five standard deviations higher than the mean weight of the obols, despite the comparable wear state of all the fractions in the study. This is a statistical variance that removes this coin from either denomination, yet its weight is half way between each, thus defining the trihemiobol. The single example of a hemiobol in the sample weighs a little more than half the mean weight of the obols. It is almost three standard deviations less than the mean obol weight; statistically an unlikely outcome were this coin intended to have been an obol.

Table 4. Coin weights.

Denomination	n	Mean (g)	Median (g)	Mode (g)	σ (g)
Drachm	49	4.06	4.16	4.20	0.34
Hemidrachm	10	2.06	2.09	-	0.14
Trihemibol	1	1.07	-	-	-
Obol	17	0.59	0.60	0.61	0.11
Hemibol	1	0.35	-	-	-

Figure 5. Histogram: drachm weights.

STATISTICS

Table 5 summarises the statistics of the catalogue of coins. The low characteristic index (n/d) of the sample of each denomination indicates that the coinage is very much under-sampled. The largest sample in the catalogue is that of the drachms, and even that only affords a meagre statistical coverage (C_{est}) of 0.57.³¹ Thus any new drachm addition to the sample has a 43 percent probability ($1 - C_{est}$) of originating from a die not represented in the sample. As a result, many more obverse dies were used to strike the coinage than are represented in the catalogue. Applying Esty's geometrical model³² to the drachm component of the catalogue yields an estimate of the original number of

³¹ Esty (2006) 359, formula (1); Esty (2011): 49, formula (3). The statistical coverage is a measure of the degree to which the sample is representative of the original sample. It defines the probability that an addition to the catalogue will have been struck by an obverse die already identified in the catalogue.

³² Esty (2011): 46 formula (1).

drachm obverse dies used to strike the coinage, albeit one associated with a very large degree of uncertainty. This estimate of 86 original dies falls within a wide range of possibilities, expressed in broad 95% confidence interval of 53-141 dies.³³ Even at the higher end of this range, it was a modest coinage of drachms, accompanied by an even smaller value of fractional denominations. A modest coinage in a range of small denominations indicates that it was struck to facilitate transactions in a local community. It was not a monetary component in inter-regional trade, or military expenditure.

Table 5. Statistics: obverse dies.

	Number (n)	Dies (d)	Index (n/d)
Drachm	51	32	1.59
Hemidrachm	10	8	1.25
Trihemiobol	1	1	1.0
Obol	17	17	1.0
Hemiobol	1	1	1.0

ORIGIN

Rapson reported that the eight specimens of the coinage which he described were “acquired from the neighbourhood of Kuh-i-Taftan.”³⁴ The latter is located in westernmost Pakistan, on the border with Iran, on the southern flank of the Sistan depression, 80 km due south of the southernmost ephemeral lake (Gaud-i-Zirreh) in the basin (Figure 6). Based on the reports of find locations,³⁵ Houghton and Lorber ascertained that the coinage originated in the region of the lower reaches of the Helmand river (the ancient Etymandros) in Sistan (Figure 6). Sustained by the inflow of the Helmand River, which brought abundant water from the Hindu Kush mountain range to the northeast, in ancient times the Sistan depression provided the only fertile agricultural landscape³⁶ in the largely desert province of ancient Drangiana.³⁷ Flanked by extensive deserts on all sides, the Sistan depression was a prosperous oasis capable of sustaining the army of Alexander the Great for two months during the winter of 330/29 BC.³⁸

At the time, the lower reaches of the Helmand River in the Sistan depression were occupied by a prosperous and independent people, the Ariaspi,³⁹ also known as the Euergetai (The King’s Benefactors) for the assistance they had rendered Cyrus the Great and his army after they emerged

³³ Esty (2006): 360, formula (4). The 95% confidence interval defines the range within which a newly calculated estimate of the original number of dies based on a new sample will fall 95% of the time. That is to say the confidence interval encompasses a range of two standard deviations around the estimate.

³⁴ Rapson (1904): 316; Kuh-i-Taftan 1902 Hoard (IGCH 1803).

³⁵ *Ibid.*: 311 and 316; Newell (1938): 159; Houghton (1980): 13; Houghton and Lorber (2002): 88-89.

³⁶ Hamzeh et al (2016): 12-13 and fig. 7 showing Iron Age-Achaemenid settlements; Engels (1978): 91-93, and map 12, for a description of the region, its location, the territory of the Ariaspi and the route of Alexander the Great’s transit of Drangiana (Zarangaea).

³⁷ Schmitt (1995): 535-7. Online edition: <http://www.iranicaonline.org/articles/drangiana> (accessed 25 August 2019).

³⁸ Huntington (1905); Fairservis (1961) 30-34; Engels (1978): 92-93; Mehrafarin (2016).

³⁹ Thomas (1906): 196; Fairservis (1961): 30-34; Engels (1978): 91-93 and map 12; Bryce (2009): 61; Mehrafarin (2016).

from the surrounding desert.⁴⁰ For this they were freed from paying annual tribute to the Persian king.⁴¹ Arrian (*Alexander* 3.27.4-5) records Alexander the Great's transit through the region in 330/29 BC noting that:

He then visited the tribe known in ancient times as the Ariaspian but later named the Euergetai, or 'Helpers,' because they had joined with Cyrus son of Cambyses in his campaign against the Scythians. When Alexander had honoured these men both for their ancestors' devotion to Cyrus and because he observed they were not governed as the other barbarians in the region were but laid claim to as great a share of justice as the most powerful of the Greeks, he left them free, and added to their domain as much of the neighbouring territory as they requested (which was very little).⁴²

Freedom, as represented by Arrian, probably involved relief from tribute and tax, as had existed under the Achaemenid regime, and a degree of autonomy under the suzerainty of the Great King. An indulgent approach to the administration of the territory of the Ariaspi is implied by the little that we know of the administrative arrangements for this territory, within the greater province of Drangiana, under both Achaemenid and Macedonian rule. Although part of Drangiana, the territory of the Ariaspi was granted the status of a minor satrapy by Alexander with its own satrap, a local named Amenides.⁴³ There is no record that the privilege granted to Ariaspian by Alexander the Great was revoked under Seleukid rule. It is probable that the Ariaspi retained a degree of autonomy, effectively a Seleukid vassal state located in Sistan.⁴⁴ One consequence of this autonomy was that it was not served by an official mint. The nearest Seleukid mints were located at Ecbatana, 1,400 km to the northwest, and Alexandria in Aria (Artocoana) 500 km to the north. The latter operated only briefly during the reigns of Antiochos II and Seleukos II.⁴⁵ Over 1,000 km to the northeast, across the Hindu Kush, an official Seleukid mint operated in Bactria during the period of the co-regency and into the reign of Antiochos II, prior to Bactrian secession from the Seleukid realm.

With the attention of a succession of Seleukid kings turned to the west of the realm, it is plausible the people of Sistan, the Ariaspi, struck the imitative victory coinage during the 3rd century BC to meet the requirement for coinage in a newly monetized local economy. Issued in the name of Antiochos, it respected Seleukid suzerainty and posed no challenge to the realm under which the Ariaspi enjoyed relative freedom and security.

⁴⁰ Diodorus Siculus *Bibliotheca historica* 17.18.1; Stronk (2017): 342; Bryce (2009) 61 and 202; Fairservis (1961): 30; Mehrafarin (2016).

⁴¹ Fairservis (1961): 30; Jacobs 2011: online edition: <http://www.iranicaonline.org/articles/achaemenid-satrapies> (accessed 25 August 2019), suggests the establishment of the Minor Satrapy of the Ariaspiae to the territory of Ariaspi. This he places between the Satrapies of Drangiana and Gedrosia.

⁴² Arrian, *Alexander* 3.27.5 in Romm, (ed.) (2010):144.

⁴³ Olbrycht (2010): 353, 358 and 366.

⁴⁴ Strootman (2008) online edition: <http://www.iranicaonline.org/articles/seleucid-empire> (accessed 25 August 2019), 'Furthermore, as the Seleucid state was a hegemonic empire, willing to acknowledge local autonomy in return for tribute, military aid and formal acknowledgment of Seleucid suzerainty, what we should rather envisage here is a shift from direct administration by royal officials to a system of vassal states, with connections established by marriage and ritualized guest-friendship, and cemented by gifts.'

⁴⁵ Houghton and Lorber (2002): 213-214 and 287-288.

conquest; possibly the foundation renamed Alexandria Prophthasia.⁴⁹ Plausibly this was the location of the mint responsible for the coinage.

CHRONOLOGY

The coinage bears the name of Antiochos, establishing a *terminus post quem* of 294 BC⁵⁰ for its earliest striking. The only documented hoard containing the coinage is the Kuh-i-Taftan Hoard (IGCH 1803), buried around 140 BC.⁵¹ This establishes a *terminus ante quem* for its emission. Houghton and Lorber⁵² posited that the coinage was struck during the co-regency of Seleukos and Antiochos, associated with latter's residency in the east. Yet the observed progressive deterioration of the iconography and epigraphy of the coinage is inconsistent with an official origin over the 14-year duration of the coregency. Houghton and Lorber's justification for a coregency date included the opinion that it "has the further advantage of bringing this rather barbarous trophy coinage closer to the prototypical series of Susa." However, significant chronological gaps are observed between many imitative coinages and their prototypes. Moreover, the legend on the coinage does not conform to the Susa prototype. It does not name Seleukos, whereas other distinctly Seleukid coin types (i.e. non-Alexandrine types) struck during the co-regency in the east bear the name of both kings. Based on the legend, it is likely that the coinage commenced during the reign of Antiochos I, or perhaps Antiochos II, with the prototype iconography selected by virtue of a preference for the message that this polysemous imagery conveyed for the Ariaspi. Otherwise, issuance in the name of Seleukos, as detailed on the Susa prototype, would be expected.⁵³

The chosen type and the legend respected the suzerain at the time of striking (Antiochos) and thus offered no challenge to Seleukid authority. Yet the progressive deterioration of the iconography and epigraphy of the coinage suggests that it was struck over an extended period involving multiple generations of copying. Although the epigraphy of the royal title underwent degradation, that of the king's name was more accurately copied. Its variant forms on the coinage of Groups 1-2 only involve the omission of the last letters of the genitive form. Unlike that which occurred with the royal title, Brahmi letters were not introduced into this component of the legend. It appears that greater attention was paid to this component of the coin's epigraphy, possibly out of respect for and a desire to cause no offence to the ruling suzerain. This suggests the possibility that Groups 1 and 2 were struck intermittently during reigns of Antiochos I (281-264 BC), Antiochos II (261-246 BC) and Antiochos III (222-187 BC).

The epigraphic developments in Group 2, particularly the introduction of the letter form D (Brahmi *dha*) to start the royal title, plus the adoption of the angular lunate *sigma* (𑀤) in the legend

⁴⁹ Recent archaeological excavations lend support the proposition of Tarn (1922): 14 that Alexandria Prophthasia 'was on or near the Hamun lake' rather than the much smaller site of Farah.

⁵⁰ Being the year that Antiochos was elevated to co-regency with his father Seleukos.

⁵¹ Rapson (1904); Kuh-i-Taftan 1902 Hoard (IGCH 1803).

⁵² Houghton and Lorber (2002): 88-89.

⁵³ The few coins issued during the co-regency that bear the name of Antiochos, which are unequivocally dated to coregency, also bear the name of Seleukos in a legend ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΣΕΛΕΚΟΥ (ΚΑΙ) ΑΝΤΙΟΧΟΥ (SC 279-283). The rare types from uncertain eastern mints bearing the legend ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΑΝΤΙΟΧΟΥ, tentatively attributed to the co-regency by Houghton and Lorber (2002), are doubtfully attributable to the coregency. Rather, they may date to the earliest year(s) of Antiochos's sole regency, although detailed study is required to resolve the chronology and attribution of these types.

strengthen the argument for the mintage of Group 2 no earlier than the middle of the third century BC. Tentatively it is suggested that Group 1 is associated with the reign of Antiochos I, while Group 2 might be associated with the period of Antiochos II, or Antiochos III.

Group 3 is distinguished by further significant degradations in the iconography and epigraphy of the coinage. An Indian influence, reflected in the exclusive use of Brahmi script in the legend, suggests that it post-dates the eastern *anabasis* of Antiochos III, if not the end of his reign. In 206 BC, Antiochos III became the first Seleukid king to visit the province of Drangiana in a century.⁵⁴ After this the history of Sistan is poorly known. No later than the second quarter of the 2nd century BC, the Sistan depression came to be occupied by the Saka from which the region took its name Sakastan, the origin of the modern-day abbreviated form, Sistan. Plausibly Group 3 marks a brief revival of the coinage in the first quarter of the 2nd century BC, prior to the occupation of Sistan by the Saka.

CONCLUSIONS

Rapson's observations on the probable imitative nature of the coinage in which he noted that when more examples became available "it is likely that the general laws which govern the changes which types undergo when they pass through a number of successive stages of unintelligent copying" will yield insight into the origin of the coinage⁵⁵ has proved prescient. Based on an expanded corpus, it appears most probable that Groups 1-3 were struck intermittently over a century commencing no earlier than 281 BC; a purely epichoric coinage. During this period the coinage underwent a progressive deterioration of epigraphy and iconography. Consideration of the historical record, find locations, and an inferred Indian influence suggest that the coinage originated among the semi-autonomous Ariaspi, the people of the Sistan depression, on the eastern fringe of the Seleukid kingdom bordering the western limit of Mauryan authority.

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Colleen Taylor contributed observations on the iconography of this coinage. Associate Professor Pankaj Tandon confirmed the possibility of Brahmi influences in the epigraphy. The images of coins in the collection of the American Numismatic Society are reproduced from the Seleucid Coins Online (SCO) database⁵⁶ under the provisions of the Open Data Commons (ODC) Open Database License (ODbL) v1.0.⁵⁷ Additional images are reproduced courtesy of the noted dealers including Classical Numismatic Group www.cngcoins.com and Roma Numismatics Limited www.RomaNumismatics.com. This study is dedicated to the memory of Boris, a wonderful companion for the last sixteen years.

⁵⁴ Schmitt (1995): 537; Houghton and Lorber 2002, 352.

⁵⁵ Rapson (1904): 321.

⁵⁶ <http://numismatics.org/sco/>

⁵⁷ <https://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/1.0/>

CATALOGUE

The catalogue is presented in the order of decreasing denomination, (drachm, hemidrachm, trihemiobol, obol and hemiobol).⁵⁸ Denoted by an asterisk adjacent to the catalogue entry are coins that are illustrated on Plates 1-3.

Obverse: Helmeted male head r., with a feline skin tied around the neck. Helmet adorned with leopard skin,⁵⁹ horns and ears of a bull.

Reverse: Nike standing r. crowning trophy. Intended legend ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΑΝΤΙΟΧΟΥ in many variant and blundered forms, some anepigraphic types; mint control, if present, located between Nike and base of trophy.

Drachms
(SC 226)

	Dies	Axes	Grams	Control	Details
Group 1.1					
1.*	A1-P1	1	4.09	IA	ANS 1984.117.12; CSE 1107; Houghton SNR 59, 9; pl. 2, 6.
2.*	A2-P2	12	3.97	? I	ANS 1984.117.5; Hoover (2009), HGC, 9, 36 (this coin); SC 198, pl. 11, 198; CSE 1037; Houghton SNR 59, pl. 1, 10. Control incompletely legible.
3.*	A3-P3	11	3.94	AA	ANS 1984.117.11; CSE 1106; Houghton SNR 59, 8; pl. 2, 5.
4.*	A4-P4	10	4.12	IA (?)	Heritage 3073 (2019), 32119. A crudely engraved second arm extends from to the r. side of Nike's torso toward the trophy. The eye on the male head is depicted in frontal rather than profile form.

⁵⁸ Excluded from the study is a tetradrachm known from a single specimen, identified in Marest Caffey, (2016), 49 imitation type Group 5, TI, illustrated on pl.21, TI, subsequently categorized as SC 226Ad. The coin has a number of anomalous characteristics. It cannot be confidently associated with SC 226-228.

⁵⁹ Frequently described as a panther skin, but more correctly and specifically it is the spotted skin of a leopard. The panther is not a distinct species but rather a general name applied to any black coloured feline of the big cat family. The leopard (*Panthera pardus*) on the other hand is a specific species, one found in the former Seleukid east, in the Hindu Kush in Afghanistan, its range extending into Pakistan and the Himalayas. As such it is the leopard skin is that portrayed on the polysemous male head identified as a conqueror of the east.

Group 1.2

5.*	A5-P5	12	4.11	CI	ANS 1984.117.10; CSE 1105; Houghton SNR 59, 7; pl. 2, 4.
6.	A5-P5	10	4.23	CI\	VAuctions 355 (2020), 22. NBJ The Art of Numismatics sku:g89.
7.*	A6-P6	12	4.06	CI?	ANS 1984.117.13; CSE 1108; Houghton SNR 59, 10; pl. 2, 7.
8.*	A7-P7	9	4.10	CD	Heritage 231951 (2019), 63102; Roma Numismatics E-Sale 57 (3019), 316.
9.*	A8-P8	9	4.14	CI	LWHT Coll. no. 314: Roma Numismatics 59 (2019), 396. A8 recut crudely over visor termination on the helmet.
10.*	A9 -P9	7	4.17	Λ	Heritage 232013 (2020), 64109; Roma E-Sale 65 (2019), 502.
11.*	A10-P10	12	4.44	off- flan	Neville Numismatics 55 (2020), 127; Roma Numismatics E-Sale 56 (2019), 483.
12.*	A10-P11	11	4.37	ΛI	Roma Numismatics E-Sale 47 (2019), 356.

Group 2.1

13.*	A11-P12	2	4.25	PI	LWHT Coll. no. 318: Roma Numismatics E-Sale 70 (2020), 821.
14.*	A12-P13	12	4.15	Λ	Hirsch 361 (2020), 2170; Hirsch 335 (2020), 1861; Hirsch 348 (2019), 438; Hirsch 343 (2018), 2388.
15.	A13-P14	3	4.22	A	Houghton SNR 59, 5; Rapson NC 4, 1 (2), pl. XVII, 2.
16.	A14-P15	10	4.22	Λ	Heritage 3067 (2018), 33204. A14 is a recut die from a well-worn and broken die with the cheek guard recut over the worn and broken original engraving.
17.*	A15-P16	12	4.44	AD	NBJ The Art of Numismatics sku:g49.
18.	A15-P16	11	4.20	AD	Künker 115 (2006), 224; Triton IX (2006), 1014.

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19.*	A16-P17	12	4.16	E	LWHT Coll. no. 317: Roma Numismatics E-Sale 64 (2019), 451. Foot of the letter E weakly engraved giving impression of F. A16 with die rust and in a later wear state than No. 20.
Group 2.2					
20.*	A16-P18	11	4.21	-	Triskeles 26 (2018), 213. A16 in less worn state than on No. 19.
21.	A16-P19	11	3.68	-	Sergey Nechayev sku:5906; Agora 63 (2016), 52; Baldwin's Argentum Auction 15 (2011), 15.
22.	A17-P20	1	4.22	-	Heritage 3073 (2019), 30172.
23.*	A17-P20	12	4.27	-	CNG eAuction 477 (2020), 175; Triskeles 24 (2018), 59.
24.	A18-P21	n.r.	4.07	-	Künker 341 (2020), 5064; Heritage 231910 (2019), 61047.
25.*	A18-P22	11	4.18	-	Roma Numismatics XIX (2020), 598; Roma Numismatics XVI (2018), 388.
26.	A18-P23	12	4.20	-	Roma Numismatics E-Sale 69 (2020), 598.
27.	A18-P23	n.r.	n.r.	-	SC pl.13, 226; NFA Winter MBS (1989), 634.
28.	A18-P24	12	4.18	-	CNG eAuction 463 (2020), 117; CNG coin shop inventory no. 507545; Pars Coins PCW-G6589.
29.	A18-P25	12	4.17	-	Heritage 232010 (2020), 61112; Roma Numismatics E-Sale 62 (2019), 501.
30.*	A19-P26	11	4.12	-	LWHT Coll. no. 315: Roma Numismatics E-Sale 61 (2019), 370.
31.	A20-P27	11	4.18	-	Heritage 3071 (2019), 33197.
32.	A20-P28	12	4.18	-	Heritage 231913 (2019), 64040.
33.	A20-P29	11	4.20	-	Roma Numismatics E-Sale 63 (2019), 305.
34.*	A20-P30	12	4.15	-	Triton XXIV (2021), 751; CNG 111 (2019), 316.
35.	A20-P30	11	4.20	-	Roma Numismatics E-Sale 68 (2020), 649.
36.*	A20recut-P31	12	4.13	-	Roma Numismatics E-Sale 60 (2019), 377. A20 recut over the forehead above the eye on a well-worn die.

37.*	A21-P32	11	4.23	-	Hirsch 361 (2020), 2171; Hirsch 335 (2020), 1862; Hirsch 348 (2019), 439; Hirsch 343 (2018), 2389.
38.*	A21-P33	10	3.79	-	ANS 1984.117.8; CSE 1103; Houghton SNR 59, 1; pl. 2, 1. ANTIOC with retrograde C.
39.	A22-P34	11	4.10	-	Heritage 231932 (2019), 62057.
40.*	A23-P35	10	3.79	-	ANS 1984.117.9; CSE 1104; Houghton SNR 59, 3; pl. 2, 3.
41.	A24-P36	12	2.92	-	Houghton SNR 59, 6; Cunningham NC IX, pl. XIII, 2. Formerly holed, now broken coin.
42.*	A25-P37	11	4.21	-	Triskeles 25 (2018), 134.
43.	A26-P38	10	4.60	-	Houghton SNR 59, 4; ESM pl. LVI, 8; Rapson NC 4, 1 (1), pl. XVII, 1.
44.	A26-P38	12	4.08	-	Heritage 231917 (2019), 64073.
45.*	A26-P38	11	4.11	-	Heritage 232015 (2020), 62138; Roma Numismatics E-Sale 66 (2020), 627.
46.	A27-P39	11	n.r.	-	Frank S. Robinson 110 (2019), 134.
47.	A28-P40	9	3.72	-	SNG Spaer 313; Houghton SNR 59, 2; pl. 2, 2. Poor quality image, die identity uncertain.
48.*	A29-P41	12	4.27	-	Spink 3014 (2003), 158, Spink 60 (1987), 140.
49.*	A30-P42	10	2.89 (?)	-	Nomos 7 (2013), 144; Leu, 83 (2002), 377. The eye on the male head is depicted in frontal rather than profile form. Crystalline and porous metal; light weight?

Group 3

50.*	A31-P43	12	3.23	Λ P	Roma Numismatics E-Sale 69 (2020), 597. Legend off-flan.
51.*	A32-P44	10	3.26	-	LWHT Coll. no. 313; Roma Numismatics E-Sale 58 (2019), 378. Crudely engraved Brahmi (?) legend, V I 1 E on l.

Hemidrachms

(SC 227)

Group 1.1

52.*	a1-p1	12	2.04	I	ANS 1984.117.16; CSE 1111; Houghton SNR 59, 16; pl. 2, 10. Mint control incorrectly described as B in CSE and VP or V in SNR 59.
53.*	a2-p2	2	1.91	CA	ANS 1984.117.15; SC pl. 13, 227; Hoover (2009), HGC 9, 50; CSE 1110; Houghton SNR 59, 15; pl. 2, 19. Control incorrectly described as V in CSE and none in SNR 59.

Group 1.2

54.*	a3-p3	9	1.90	CO	ANS 1984.117.14; CSE 1109; Houghton SNR 59, 11; pl. 2, 8. Mint control incorrectly described as EB in CSE and SNR 59.
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Group 2.1

55.*	a4-p5	10	2.2	Λ	Gorny & Mosch 261 (2019), 370. Legend: CIEAI with retrograde E.
56.	a5-p5	12	2.09	Λ	Houghton SNR 59, 13; ESM pl. LVI, 9; Rapson NC 4, 1 (4), pl. XVII, 4.
57.	a6-p6	11	2.19	ΛI	Leu Numismatik 4 (2019), 375.
58.*	a6-p6	10	2.17	ΛI	Roma Numismatics XVII (2019), 563. ΛI mint control weakly struck on flan edge.
59.	a6-p6	9	2.16	ΛI	Houghton SNR 59, 12; Rapson NC 4, 1 (3), pl. XVII, 3. Control off-flan.

Group 2.2

60.	a7-p7	12	2.08	-	Houghton SNR 59, 14; Rapson NC 4, 1 (5), pl. XVII, 5.
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Group 3

61.	a8-p8	10	1.82	-	Rapson NC 4, 2, pl. XVII, 8. Barely recognizable helmeted head. Nike and trophy facing l.; retrograde engraving?
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Trihemiobol

(SC -)

Group 3

62.*	O1-R1	6	1.07	-	CNG eAuction 369 (2016), 345. O1 with extremely crude highly abstracted form, lacking facial features.
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Obols

(SC 228)

Group 1.1

63.	o1-r1	12	0.72	?	Houghton <i>SNR</i> 59, 19; Rapson <i>NC</i> 4, 1 (7), pl. XVII, 7. Mint control struck off flan.
64.*	o2-r2	2	0.65	A?	ANS 1984.117.22; CSE 1117; Houghton <i>SNR</i> 59, 24.
65.*	o3-r3	10	0.59	AI	ANS 1984.117.21; CSE 1116; Houghton <i>SNR</i> 59, 23.
66.	o4-r4	12	n.r	CA	SC pl. 13, 228.2; London, BM Coll.
67.*	o5-r5	2	0.65	CA	ANS 1984.117.17; CSE 1112; Houghton <i>SNR</i> 59, 17.
68.	o6-r6	7	0.60	CA	CNG 36 (1996), 623.

Group 1.2

69.	o7-r7	6	0.56	Λ?	ANS1984.117.19; CSE 1114; Houghton <i>SNR</i> 59, 21.
70.*	o8-r8	10	0.60	-	ANS 1984.117.23; CSE 1118; Houghton <i>SNR</i> 59, 25. Broken coin in two pieces.
71.	o9-r9	5?	0.54		Künker 193 (2011), 281; CNG 47 (1998), 533. Broken, worn, and corroded.
72.*	o10-r10	7	0.61	-	ANS 1984.117.20; CSE 1115; Houghton <i>SNR</i> 59, 22.
73.	o11-r11	7	0.61	-	Künker 304 (2018), 628.
74.*	o12-r12	12	0.43	-	ANS 1984.117.18; CSE 1113; Houghton <i>SNR</i> 59, 20.
75.*	o13-r13	9	0.61	-	ANS 1944.100.74127; Naville X (1925), 803.

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Group 2.1

76.	o14-r14	10	0.73	A	Houghton <i>SNR</i> 59, 18; <i>ESM</i> pl. LVI, 7; Rapson <i>NC</i> 4, 1 (6), pl. XVII, 6. Rapson correctly read control as A, Houghton as Λ.
77.*	o15-r15	1	0.40	A	National Museum of Iran Collection INM 43306; Zahra Alinezhad (forthcoming) <i>Coins of the Seleucid Empire from the National Museum of Iran</i> no. 47.

Group 2.2

78.*	o16-r16	12	0.41	-	CNG 109 (2018), 207; CNG eAuction 357 (2018), 148. Broken coin.
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Group 3

79.*	o17-r16	3	0.79	-	ANS 1984.117.24; CSE 1119.
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Houghton *SNR* 59, 27 records another obol; Joel Malter 4 (1978), 263, weighing 0.46 grams, with die axes adjusted to 1h. No image of the coin could be located.

**Hemiobol
(SC -)**

Group 2.2

80.	o18-p17	6	0.35	-	CNG 47 (1998), 534.
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Plate 1

Drachms

Group 1, Series 1

Group 1, Series 2

Group 2, Series 1

Plate 2

Drachms

Group 2, Series 2

20

23

25

30

34

36

37

38

40

42

45

48

49

Group 3

50

51

Plate 3

Hemidrachms (enlarged x 1.5)

Trihemionbol (enlarged x 2)

Obols (enlarged x 2)

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